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**19th International Conference
on Chemistry and the Environment**
Belgrade, Serbia, June 8-12, 2025

Environmental Chemistry for Sustainability

E-Book of Abstracts

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**19th International Conference on Chemistry
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E-Book of Abstracts

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Dear participants, welcome to Belgrade!

On behalf of the Division of Chemistry and the Environment (DCE) (<https://www.euchems.eu/divisions/chemistry-and-the-environment-2/>) of the European Association of the Chemical Societies (EuChemS) (<https://www.euchems.eu/>), the Serbian Chemical Society (<https://www.shd.org.rs/en/>), and the local organizing committee, it is our great pleasure and privilege to warmly welcome you to the 19th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment (ICCE 2025).

This prestigious event, which gathers nearly 350 participants from across the globe is hosted by the Serbian Chemical Society with the support of the University of Belgrade and the University of Novi Sad.

At a time when continued scientific progress is essential to ensure a healthy environment and a sustainable future, ICCE 2025 addresses key challenges and emerging developments, advances knowledge and inspires action through the lens of Environmental Chemistry. In addition to the main program running in fourteen parallel sessions, ICCE 2025 will feature four pre-conference satellite events, each dedicated to current research priorities and strategic environmental topics and EuChemS DCE Career Award lecture by Terry Frank Bidleman from Sweden. The scientific program includes seven plenary lectures including two Distinguished Lectures from the American Chemical Society, and fourteen keynote lectures that introduce parallel sessions, comprising 175 oral and 156 poster presentations. A Special Editorial Panel Discussion, with editors from leading international scientific journals, will provide valuable insight into the evolving landscape of scientific publishing.

ICCE 2025 provides an excellent platform for networking, exchange of ideas and collaboration. Our collective mission is to deepen understanding of pollutant's cycling, and their fate and effects in the environment, while advancing pollution prevention and waste management. The latest developments in environmental analysis, pollution monitoring and risk assessment directly impact societal response to environmental challenges, which inevitably focus on various sustainability strategies. To be effective, these responses must be supported by excellent knowledge-based tools and societal inspiration, both offered by ICCE 2025.

We hope that you will not only enjoy the rich scientific program but also take-home memorable experiences from Serbia!

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Special thanks to the Evertéa Foundation, which generously provided registration grants to a number of students and early-career researchers from around the world who would otherwise not have had the opportunity to attend. Additionally, the best oral and poster presentations will be recognized and awarded by the Local Organizing Committee, with Springer eBook vouchers as prizes.

Roland Kallenborn, EuChemS DCE Chairman, Antonio Marcomini, previous ICCE 2023 Chairman and Philippe Garrigues, Editor-in-Chief of *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* provided us with valuable guidance in shaping the format and structure of this year's conference in line with the ICCE tradition. The input of all EuChemS DCE members was instrumental in refining the scientific program, selecting invited speakers, and ensuring a robust and fair abstract review process. We deeply appreciate the support of our colleagues from partner associations as George Cobb, John Giesy and Virender Kumar Sharma from Division on Environmental Chemistry of the American Chemical Society (ACSEnv), Roberto Terzano, Hemda Garelick and Melanie Kah from International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry (IUPAC) and Takeshi Nakano from Japan Society for Environmental Chemistry for helping us to make this event remarkable.

Company "Congrexpo" d.o.o., our professional conference organizer, led by Mrs. Olivera Popović, manages all logistics and technical coordination with dedication and professionalism. The Hotel M team, under the direction of Mrs. Jelena Jakovljević, ensures a welcoming and pleasant experience for all participants in the warm and familiar setting of one of Belgrade's most established congress venues. A very special "thank you" goes to our volunteers Slaven Tenodi, Tijana Marijanović, Sanja Vasiljević, Dušan Rakić, Marija Simić, Katarina Stojanović, Marija Kovačević, Ana Lazić, and Lazar Popović.

We thank all the participants for their oral and poster presentations which make the ICCE2025 shining!

Professor Ivana Ivančev-Tumbas,
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Impact of organic soil amendments on the sorption of cypermethrin and cyprodinil in Danube alluvial soil

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To investigate the differential impact of organic soil amendments (OSA) on the sorption behaviour of two selected pesticides cypermethrin (a pyrethroid insecticide) and cyprodinil (a fungicide) – batch adsorption experiments were conducted using enriched sandy material from the Danube River. The experiments were performed at room temperature ($20\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), with equilibrium achieved after 72 hours. Sorption isotherms were modelled using the Freundlich model, with calculated sorption coefficients (K_F) and nonlinearity factors (n) confirming good model fit ($R^2 = 0.989\text{--}0.999$). The n values ranged from 0.56 to 1.28, indicating variations in sorption favorability depending on the soil amendment composition. Additionally, partition coefficients (K_d) were determined at three equilibrium concentrations ($C_e = 0.01S_w$, $0.1S_w$, $0.5S_w$), covering a broad solubility range, with K_d values between 2.2 and 5.3, further highlighting the influence of soil amendments on pesticide retention.

The study examined the effects of different organic amendments, including biochar, sediment, and compost, incorporated in various soil mixtures. Biochar was produced from *Miscanthus giganteus* at 550°C , sediment was dredged from the Begej Canal in Serbia (contaminated with heavy metals and organic pollutants), and compost was derived from green waste in Novi Sad. The results demonstrated that sorption behavior strongly depends on the type and composition of the organic amendment used. Cyprodinil ($\log K_{ow} = 4.6$) exhibited higher sorption capacity in soil mixtures containing biochar, compost, and sediment, likely due to hydrogen bond formation with nitrogen-containing functional groups. In contrast, cypermethrin ($\log K_{ow} = 6.4$) displayed greater sorption affinity in mixtures containing sediment or biochar combined with compost, suggesting the predominance of hydrophobic interactions. The variations in sorption efficiency highlight the complexity of pesticide retention mechanisms in amended soils and the necessity of tailored amendment strategies for different pesticide types.

These findings confirm that the sorption and mobility of pesticides are significantly influenced by the presence and composition of organic soil amendments, which in turn affect their potential for leaching into groundwater. The results suggest that biochar, sediment, and compost can be effectively utilized to enhance pesticide retention in soils, thereby reducing environmental contamination. Understanding these interactions is essential for developing sustainable soil management practices that minimize pesticide transport while maintaining soil fertility and environmental quality.

Keywords: soil, OSA, pesticides, groundwater contamination, sorption isotherms

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